

MARITIME INFRASTRUCTURE AND SHIPPING BUSINESS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between maritime infrastructure and shipping business in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between ship traffic and the maritime infrastructure, the relationship between ship turnaround time and the maritime infrastructure, the relationship between average time awaiting berth and maritime infrastructure. Ship traffic or throughput, ship turnaround time and average time awaiting berth were used as proxy for shipping business while maritime infrastructure was proxied by number of ship, vessel capacity and port infrastructure. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. Data were obtained CBN statistical bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics bulletin, Nigeria Port Authority Bulletin and World Development indicators several years. Ordinary least square estimation technique was used to estimate the relationship among the variables of interest. Finding showed that maritime infrastructure does not significantly impact on shipping business in Nigeria. This is believed to be as a result of poor performance of governance indicators in Nigeria. In view of the finding, it was recommended that Port infrastructure and other maritime infrastructure could be improved through diligent concessionary arrangement and that there is need to decongest the over bloated port by building and expanding new ports in the country such as Ibom deep sea port.

Keywords: Maritime, Infrastructure, Shipping Business, Nigeria, Port Infrastructure, Ship Capacity.

1 Introduction

Background to the Study

Essentially, two common forms of infrastructure have been defined by the World

Bank and other international institutions to include; Physical and Social infrastructure. Physical infrastructure typically involves the network of transport, communication, operational and public services that together function as a system. Examples of physical infrastructure include public utilities such as power, telecommunication, water supply, sanitation and sewage, waste collection and disposal, intermodal transport modes including roads, railways, seaports, waterways and airports. Social infrastructure on the hand, involves a set of beneficial services meant for the improvement of the general well-being of the citizenry. Examples of social infrastructure items include health care services, schools and other services that are considered indispensable for economic development. These two forms of infrastructure are necessary for the smooth operation of the shipping business in Nigeria (Afolabi, 2015). However, for the purpose of this study, we shall be particular about maritime infrastructure and how they affect operations of the shipping sector in Nigeria.

By maritime infrastructure, we mean an umbrella term for all those activities and facilities that support and enhance the maritime transport sector and make it efficient, productive, safe and environmentally friendly, reinforced by an effective regulatory framework – all combined to make the sector deliver on its fundamental objectives. According to AAPA (2014), maritime “infrastructure” is generally thought of as cranes, wharves, dredged channels, locks, dams and other tangible structures. Consequently, marine transportation system consists of the following main physical components: navigable waters, vessels (publicly and privately owned), ports (harbor and land-side facilities), intermodal connections (highway and railway), shipyards, and repair facilities. Port infrastructure on the other hand, includes docks, piers, channel harbors, and more. In general, the conditions from terminal to terminal within a port vary. However, all ports are challenged to maintain their infrastructure in harsh marine environments (infrastructure report card, 2021).

The maritime industry includes all enterprises engaged in the business of designing, constructing, manufacturing, acquiring, operating, supplying, repairing and/or maintaining vessels, or component parts thereof: of managing and/or operating shipping lines, stevedoring and customs brokerage services, shipyards, dry docks, marine railways, marine repair shops, shipping and freight forwarding services and similar enterprises. Put succinctly, the industry embraces all the maritime related business activities which take place within the country’s maritime environment. These include offshore economic activities such as fishing, salvage, towage, underwater resources and on-shore economic activities such as port activities, maritime transport (shipping), ship construction, repairs and maintenance activities (Ekpo, 2012; Brickstone, 2019).

Shipping can be seen as a physical process of transporting goods and cargo, by land, air and sea. It can also describe the movement of objects by ship, land or “ground” shipping can be by train or by truck. In air and sea shipments, ground transportation is often still required to take the product from its origin to the airport or seaport and then to its destination, ground transportation typically more affordable than air shipments but more expensive than shipping by sea (Ekeada, Obioma & Anyanwu, 2018).

A striking feature of the shipping business to outsiders is the different characters of the companies in different sections of the industry. For example, liner companies and bulk shipping companies belong to the same industry but they seem to have little else in similarity. In fact, there are several different groups of companies involved in the transport chain, some directly and others indirectly. The direct players are the cargo owners, often the primary producers such as oil companies and the shipping companies. Because shipping is a service business, ship demand depends on several factors including price, speed reliability and security (Benson and David, 2018.). The role of shipping and shipping services needs to be strengthened to secure the foundation from which to develop more innovative and competitive solutions in the manufacture of equipment, shipbuilding, logistic and transport services.

The growth of international trade demands that all trading nations, not just the few, should contribute to the security of trade routes. The demand for shipping worldwide is increasing, so new and innovative ways of transporting cargoes present designers and engineers with opportunities. (Maritime foundation, 2016). The survival of the maritime industry in Nigeria depends to a large extent on the level of aggregate demand for shipping services and the country’s shipping lines market share. The latter hugely depends on the operational efficiency of the lines and the former on how well the country is performing.

Maritime industry plays a prominent role in the economy of such countries as Singapore, Belgium and the United States of America. As a matter of fact, events around the world have shown that the maritime sector, when handled rightly, can go a long way in the reduction of poverty, wealth creation, skills acquisition promotion and encouraging entrepreneurship. The maritime sector, if well harnessed, not only has the capacity to boost a country’s economic development but also contribute very significantly to the growth of the national gross domestic product (GDP). Some of the opportunities the sector can bring include: providing a platform for global shipping and commerce; act as a source of renewable energy; enabling fisheries, tourism, maritime transport and infra-structure, to mention but a few.

Throughout its history, Nigeria has been a global maritime nation, depending upon the oceans for economy, welfare, and defense. In the modern era, emphasis on

globalization and the world economy has increased this dependence considerably. Nigeria, located on the coastline corridors of the Gulf of Guinea and the Bight of Benin, is blessed with a natural maritime endowment base comprising a coastline of over 850kms, an exclusive economic zone of over 200 nautical miles, a vast inland waterways resource estimated at nearly 4,000kms, capable of supporting a vibrant intra-regional trade. With Nigeria 's total annual freight cost, estimated at between \$5 billion and \$6 billion annually, there is no doubt that shipping is of great importance to the Nigerian economy (NIMASA, 2018).

Due to close linkage between shipping activities and economic development, most nations cannot afford to treat it with levity, hence a conscious intervention is needed to ensure that the national interest is protected. Ekpo (2012) observes that shipping as a primary logistics provider is critical in the process of Nigeria's international trade and economic development. As a mode of transport, shipping provides the cheapest and most efficient means of moving large volumes of import and export round the world thereby creating jobs and adding value to the economy. It can be admitted from the foregoing that maritime infrastructure is crucial in maintaining this link to the sea. From naval bases to commercial ports, maritime infrastructure if well-developed nationwide can be crucial to both the economic sector and military strategy. Maritime infrastructure is critical to the employment of national maritime power and as such is a logical (if not desirable) target for acts of terrorism by the enemies of the state. A successful attack against a port could incur serious economic and military damage, present an enemy with the opportunity to inflict mass casualties, and have serious long-term detrimental effects on the national economy (Watts, 2005).

The laudable role play by shipping notwithstanding, Nigeria's national shipping industry is in crises due to poor development of maritime infrastructure perhaps as a result of investment difficulties, management inefficiency and organizational problems among others. Poor maritime infrastructure no doubt can hinder the growth of the shipping business in Nigeria and this invariably could hamper the growth rate of the economy. To what extent could maritime infrastructure affect the growth and sustainability of shipping business in Nigeria. The essence of this study is to investigate this.

Statement of the Problem

Ships have the largest carrying capacity of any freight mode and maritime ports handle more freight than all other types of terminal combined. Thus, shipping infrastructure requirements are substantial. The infrastructure elements include port terminals (docking areas, bunkering, shore-side power, storage); port operational equipment (cranes, tugboats, dredgers) and man-made global maritime routes. Port terminals usually provide specialised facilities (cranes, grabs, storage) for different types of cargo.

Vessel capacity at container ports is measured in TEUs, or “twenty-foot equivalents,” which equals one 20-foot container. Maximum vessel capacity in Nigeria for inward cargo had doubled in size from 356,551 TEUs in 2007 to 771,130 TEUs in 2015. Consequently, the maximum vessel capacity for outward cargo increased from 75,399 TEU’s in 2007 to 168,249 TEU’s in 2017. As vessels have increased in size, port infrastructure — including berths, cranes, and channel depths require investment to keep pace.

The Nigerian Ports Statistics 2012 – 2017 reflected that ship traffic at the Nigerian ports recorded a total of 4,175 ocean going vessels with 131,569,821 gross registered tonnages in 2017 as against 4,622 ocean going vessels with 134,2,13,076 gross registered tonnages in 2016. Similarly, a total of 12,243 service boats with 5, 910,406 gross registered tonnages was recorded in 2017 as against 9,418 service boats with 5,193,402 gross registered tonnages in 2016. Also, cargo traffic statistics revealed a total of 71,903,266 cargo traffic was recorded at all Nigerian ports in 2017 as against 70,819,092 cargo traffic in 2016. 43,019,889 of the cargo traffic were inwards while 28,883,377 were outward. A total of 181,404 vehicle traffic was recorded in 2017 at all the ports as against 105,189 and 131,994 vehicle traffic in 2016 and 2015 respectively.

The number of passenger traffic at the Calabar Port within the period under review was put at 6,704 in 2017 as against 7,442 in 2016. The volume of inward and outward tonnage of cargo and human traffic at Nigeria’s ports fluctuate perhaps due to some factors the most important of which could be dearth of infrastructures at the ports of berth. Port operations such as scheduling of arriving vessels, allocation of wharf space and cranes to serve the vessels, loading and unloading of cargoes, yard operation and gate operations are enhanced through the provision and availability of efficient port infrastructure. Hence, efficient port infrastructure and operations is reflected in the volume of cargo and revenue generated by the port, which acts as a boost to the economy.

Greater efficiency in Transport has been pursued recently in many countries by changing the structure and institutional framework of the industry. These changes have been introduced by such measures as privatization and deregulation so that the role of government, Federal governments in particular will be reduced significantly.

The Maritime industry has been subject to similar development. However, in most third world countries like Nigeria changes in maritime and port policies have been modest. The countries in which the policy changes have been greatest are those in which national policies exerted strong influence on port performance. In the light of the above argument, there emerged two decades ago, the National Shipping Policy otherwise known as Decree No.10 of 1987 which came into force in 1988

establishing the then National Maritime Authority(NMA). Since its inception, the then National Maritime Authority had created a laudable impact on the maritime industry, which in turn has a big role to play in national economic development. Nigeria has a highly productive open sea with abundant and diverse maritime resources.

However, Nigeria has not been able to maximize the advantage of these natural resources. Rather, she has in the last half a century, witnessed a chequered history in the development of her maritime industry and shipping to be precise. Earlier than the period 1959, the maritime industry of Nigeria was exclusively owned, managed and controlled by her colonial master and its international maritime business allies. Essentially, the cyclic theory of port oscillation is manifest in port concentration and diffusion, which could be attributed to the then trend in cargo throughput of the country's port.

This situation was not peculiar to Nigeria alone as many other African countries also found it extremely difficult to take part in the maritime business of their country. The ports were managed by these foreigners who handled exclusively the import and export cargo. Therefore, the benefits that should accrue to a country in the management of her maritime industry went to the foreigners. Today, the shipment of cargo into and out of Nigeria mostly depends on foreign shipping lines. More so, in spite of the "National Shipping Policy", Nigeria faces a crisis of extinction from her maritime industry. Perhaps, the country needs to know what it is losing to be able to adequately address this problem. Maybe, the passage of the coastal and inland shipping Act, 2003 by the National Assembly seems to mark a new beginning in the shipping and maritime administration in Nigeria. The rebirth of National Maritime Authority (NMA) to Nigerian Maritime administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA) should create room for efficiency in the maritime sector while the carotage regime is expected to increase to a reasonable extent, indigenous participation in maritime business. In view of the aforesaid, this study seeks to investigate the extent to which shipping activities in Nigeria could be influenced by the infrastructure at each Nigeria's port of berth.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between maritime infrastructure and shipping business in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to;

- i. examine the relationship between ship traffic and the maritime infrastructure.
- ii. examine the relationship between ship turnaround time and the maritime infrastructure.
- iii. examine the relationship between average time awaiting berth and maritime infrastructure.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

It is the constitutional role and duty of Government to drive the sustainable development of the state through programmes and policies aimed at optimizing public social welfare, economic growth and living standard within the state (Nwokedi *et al.*, 2020). The theories of transport development emphasizes transport as the forerunner of human, economic and sustainable development and as such, transport infrastructure investment policies and programmes of government aimed at providing mobility to the people, economic goods and services, and improving utility derivable from social and economic transactions in goods and services must be based on expected benefits to the public, and/or profitability potentials to the private operators with interest in investment in the given transport infrastructure. The lack, absence of and/or inadequacy in investment in these infrastructures in any mode of transport be it road, maritime, aviation, rail, pipeline etc., results in transport infrastructure deficit and under supply situation which presents the society with accessibility problems, such that a section of the society in need of transport which is an essential public good cannot adequately access it (Alstadt, 2012). The resultant negative effect is multiple but manifest via immobility of society, economic goods and services etc., leading to social deprivation, economic recession, non-sustainability of earlier achieved growth, economic blight and underdevelopment. The continuous conscious drive by governments to ensure adequate investment in transport infrastructure is motivated by the above facts.

Traditionally, seaports have become a strategic economic endowment and major catalyst of globalization process (UNCTAD, 2009) as almost 80% of the total global trade volume is facilitated by ocean transportation (Shan *et al.*, 2014). As an interface between sea and land transportation, ports have constituted a core of the transport system and the economic determinant of any state that owns them. The significance of ports has been massified by the now global maritime trade influencer called container. Containers have been described by Urry (2007) as a mobility-system which produced complex and paradoxical effects in transport system. It is the object of the most advanced form of unitization called containerization. In the purview of economic geography, containerization has been seen as a facilitator of international trade (Coe *et al.*, 2008). The objective of containerization is to achieve optimum advantages of through-movement of freights. As described by Levinson (2006), container is at the core of a highly automated system for moving goods from anywhere, to anywhere, with minimum of cost and complication on the way. Apart from cost minimization, introduction of containerization has lowered time expended in transferring freight from manufacturer to consumer, as well as time spent in storage yard (Olapoju, 2019).

Overtime, the maritime industry has substantially changed from an industry that was always international in its character to a truly global entity with routes that span across hemispheres, transporting raw materials, spare parts and finished goods. Maritime transportation plays a major role in the national and international trade and economic growth. The seaborne trade represents over 90% of the international trade in the world.

Port operations such as scheduling of arriving vessels, allocation of wharf space and cranes to serve the vessels, loading and unloading of cargoes, yard operation and gate operations are enhanced through the provision and availability of efficient port infrastructure. Hence, efficient port infrastructure and operations is reflected in the volume of cargo and revenue generated by the port, which acts as a boost to the economy (Omoke *et al.*, 2018).

Port operations is very vital to Nigerian economy. Data obtained from port operations data can indicate if a port is efficient or not. The number of vessels that called at the port in 2016 had a decline of 2.72% when compared to the previous year. Also comparing the operations data to that of the neighbouring ports shows that the performances of the neighbouring ports are more robust. Hence, Nigerian port operations need to be reviewed to enable the ports to improve their competitive position in the regional and global market. Port congestions, high container dwell time, high turnaround time of vessels and trucks, inadequate of port facilities such as berths, etc. have tremendously negated the operational performance of Nigerian ports. These drawbacks in port activities have made Nigeria's ports operationally inefficient leading to increases in demurrage charges and operating cost of vessels. The implied economic implication of the aforementioned inefficiencies is that most shippers will prefer to call at other ports with less congestion, better port facilities and sophisticated cargo handling equipment. The economy is also experiencing increases in the prices of consumable goods, cut-off-flow during operations by the production companies, decrease in per capital income of port employees and general decreases in the revenue accruable to the port.

Onwuegbuchunam *et al.*, (2021) assert that Ports have significant influence on volume and conditions of trade as well as economic development of developing nations. On the other hand, speed in cargo handling and distribution impact on port efficiency and productivity. Effective and efficient utilization of cargo handling equipment in port operations contribute immensely to port productivity.

In terms of services offered to vessels at the ports, Hart posits that vessel's turnaround time is highly influenced by cargo handling performance. The application of automated systems and skilled labour in cargo handling operations therefore, are essential in ensuring timely operations, reduction in human errors, improvement in

quality of service and reduced cost of operation. Ports with modern berths and cargo handling equipment systems have the capacity to offer competitive international transport distribution services since they attract modern tonnage. The overall cost of transportation from one port to another is influenced by speed with which cargo is handled. However, additional time spent in loading or discharging alternative ports' cargo could translate to additional cost to port users such as shippers and ship owners. As noted by Branch, the failure of a port to modernize its berths and associated cargo-handling systems could encourage ship-owners and shippers to use others. Accordingly, the need to eliminate inefficiencies in shipping logistics and improve operational efficiency in Nigerian ports necessitated port reforms involving concessioning of Nigerian seaports to private terminal operators in the year 2006. There have been some major investments in cargo handling equipment in the ports by private terminal operators. It has been noted that the investments in cargo handling equipment by the private terminal operators in Nigerian ports have resulted in improved cargo throughputs and vessel traffic.

Available data show that as at 2013, about 98 percent of the sea freight in Nigeria was still done by foreign companies and that foreigners make up about 85% of the maritime workforce in Nigeria (Global shipbuilding Market Report, 2013). According to the 2017 report of the National Bureau of Statistics/Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA), the ship traffic statistics at Nigerian ports has reflected that a total number of 19,833 vessels berthed at the various ports between 2013 and 2016. Similarly, 543,842,425 tonnages were registered within the period under review. Year 2014 recorded the highest number of vessels berthed as well as tonnages registered while the least were recorded in 2016. Tin Can Island Port handled the most ships accounting for 33% of total number of ships that berthed in all ports and 32% of total tonnage registered in all ports. It is closely followed by Apapa port which accounted for 28% of ships that berthed and 25% of total tonnage registered and Onne port which accounted for 15% of ships that berthed and 30% of total tonnage registered. Also, cargo traffic statistics revealed a total of 312,185,808 cargo traffic was recorded at all Nigerian ports between 2013 and 2016. 196,851,236 or 63% of the cargo traffic were inwards while 115, 334572 or 37% were outward (National Bureau of Statistics/Nigerian Ports Authority, 2017).

Basically, the port system is approved to ensure good import-export goods and exchanges between regions in the country, meeting the needs of socio-economic development. However, the greatest current problem is the asynchrony between seaports and interconnected infrastructure. Asynchronous in scale, especially in the process of implementation between the investment projects to build technical infrastructure connected to the port (including the port entrance and logistics hub) greatly affect port performance and efficiency (Nguyen, 2018). In recent years,

despite many efforts in new construction as well as upgrading and modernization of existing seaports, the infrastructure of the port system in Nigeria is still weak in terms of management and exploitation. and backwardness in science and technology compared to advanced countries.

Meanwhile, Munim and Schramm (2018), assert that many countries are planning to build up regional hub ports, following successful cases such as Singapore, Shenzhen, Hong Kong, Dubai, to name a few and expecting additional growth of their economies in forms of new service markets. This could be aided by developing transshipment facility and efficient transport network. However, the port–city relationship has changed and the urban structure of cities is no longer important for explaining the intensity and spatial distribution of maritime transport networks (Ducruet *et al.*, 2016). Slack and Gouvernal (2015) argued that the potential for economic development through hub port development is more limited than suggested in most maritime literature. Due to structural changes in the global shipping industry, neither a port’s throughput projection nor its economic contribution performs with the degree of certainty expected by the planners (Hesse, 2006). Also, the demolition of the shipping conference system in 2008 and the global financial crisis in 2009 hit the shipping industry adversely (Munim and Schramm, 2017). According to Grossmann (2008), “economic growth has shifted to newer economic sectors which require investments into different locational factors, a high quality of life and an attractive, well function city-core”. Hence, before investing millions of dollars in building up or expanding port infrastructure, it is important to understand the extent to which ports impact national or regional economy.

Portugal-Perez and Wilson (2012) note that investments in physical infrastructure creates a better business environment and improves transport efficiency, which facilitates export growth. Similarly, Yeo *et al.* (2008) found that quality of port service, logistics costs, regional connectivity, hinterland condition and port accessibility, contributes significantly to a port’s competitiveness. Hence, a combination of infrastructure quality, hinterland accessibility and productivity plays a vital role in strengthening a port’s competitive position. Gordon *et al.* (2005) added that a combination of port facilities, including sufficient investment, supportive government policies, excellence in operation and information technology, can help a port attain sustainable competitiveness, which will produce higher seaborne trade compared to the less competitive ports.

Lakshmanan (2011) proposed that investment into transport facilities improves logistics ability and reduces freight costs. Wilmsmeier and Hoffmann (2008) estimated the role of liner shipping connectivity (LSC) and port infrastructure in determining freight rates in the Caribbean. They found that a one-standard-deviation

increase in LSC implies an expected reduction of USD 287 in freight rate, and that a one-standard deviation increase in port infrastructure for an importing country implies an expected reduction of USD 225 in freight rate. Furthermore, Sánchez *et al.* (2003) found that freight costs are lower in efficient ports after controlling for distance, liner service availability, type of product and insurance costs. Also, an increase in port efficiency from the 25th to the 75th percentile is expected to reduce shipping costs by 12% (Clark *et al.*, 2004). Quality of infrastructure and transport costs are important for export-led economic growth (Limao and Venables, 2001). Thus, it can be derived that efficient ports have better quality infrastructure and logistics performance than inefficient ones. Additionally, an efficient port system with enhanced logistic abilities is a key determinant of foreign direct investment into a country (Panayides *et al.*, 2015). On the other hand, inefficient ports reduce national and international trade and affect economic growth adversely (Clark *et al.*, 2004). Also, the role of ports in the internationalization process of business firms was highlighted by Ellis (2011).

Korinek and Sourdin (2011) observe that a country's logistics performance plays a vital role in facilitating transportation of goods to the international market. "Inefficient logistics services impede trade by imposing an extra cost in terms of time as well as money". Limao and Venables (2001) found a significant negative association between transport cost and international trade. Long customs clearance time adversely affects firms' total factor productivity (Subramanian *et al.*, 2005). Meanwhile, a better business environment comprising quality logistics services is associated with better export performance. Overall, firms in countries with better logistics performance have higher probability of exporting to international markets and attracting foreign direct investments (Hausman *et al.*, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by the theory of constraints and location theory.

The Theory of Constraint (TOC)

The theory of constraints (TOC) is a project management tool which opines that all manageable projects and systems are capable of being limited from adequately achieving its set objectives by a few constraints (Goldratt, 1984). It states that there is at least one principal constraint that inhibits a system from fully achieving its objectives. The TOC therefor concentrates efforts at identifying the principal constraint and restructuring the rest of the organization from being hindered from fully achieving its set objectives. This means that processes, organizations, systems etc., are vulnerable since the weakest non-performing or negatively performing component of it can always cause damage and stop the system and /or organization from maximizing productivity and/or performance. The theory of constraints (TOC)

is viewed an overall management philosophy developed by E. M. Goldratt in a book titled 'The Goal'. It aims to help organizations continually reach their goals by adopting a management strategy that helps them to deal with the worst identified constraints.

Goldratt (2004), states that to fully meet a target objective; conditions exist that must be met in the first place. Some of these conditions may include but not limited to: initial investment, regulatory and legal obligations, safety, etc., thus any of the condition not properly and adequately met constitutes constraints to the target of maximization of throughput and productivity improvement. For most private businesses like ship building, the objective is to maximize profit; for other firms, making profit may be a necessary step for driving towards other objectives. For example, ship building industry is a multimillion dollar capital intensive and technology driven industry and a foreign currency earner for ship building countries. It equally creates massive jobs that aids in boosting the GDP of ship building countries empowering such countries above others in the political and economic exploitation of the oceans and sea trade to their greater advantage (Nwokedi *et al.*, 2019). But to develop the ship building industrial sector which is largely driven by private sector investments and position Nigeria for example as a ship building, recycling and repair giant, the privately owned ship yards must first be able to make profits and survive the vicissitudes of the trade; it is the survival of the private ship yards through sustained profit earnings that will subsequently ensure the growth of the ship building sector and emergence of Nigeria as a ship building nation at the long run. One may thus argue that the achievement of the goal of developing viable ship yards and ship building sector in Nigeria is limited by at least one or few principal constraints which must be surmounted in order that the sector may achieve the much-needed development.

The argument by Qui, Fredendall and Zhu (2002), is that if there was nothing preventing a firm, organization, industry or system from achieving the highest level of performance and productivity; its performance and productivity will take values up to infinite. This has however been proved to be impossible in a real-life setting for reason that production processes are fraught with constraints. Suffice it to say that if the ship building and repair industry in Nigeria is not fraught with bottlenecks and constraints, the productivity and development of the sector would be infinite. The very poor and undeveloped form in which it currently exists, suggests the prevalence of principal constraints which must be adequately addressed in order that growth may commence in the sector. High import duties, tariff and other fiscal policies constitute major challenges that has crippled ship yards and ship building investments in Nigeria and scared away potential investors in the sector (Akinola, 2015; Fashakin, 2017).

Location Theory

The Weberian location theory is about cost minimization around triangles (Onifade, 2020). The theory opines that the location of a facility should be based on minimum costs of transportation. In other words, it is assumed that there are two places, A and B, from which materials are to be carried to market P. The theory suggests that the least cost of transportation between the two places is to be selected. Though the assumption of same cost of transportation for both raw materials and finished goods has been faulted about this postulation, it is still useful in port location and transportation feasibility studies. The seaports cannot have the same potential to generate traffic in maritime logistics. According to Haezendonck & Notteboom (2002), it was observed that there are so many factors than can be responsible for the demand of a particular seaport. One such factor was competition. Parola *et al.* (2017), however, disagreed by saying that competition is different from competitiveness, in which the latter connotes the ability of the port to add value to generate more traffic than others. Heaver *et al.* (2001) found out that location is one major factor that can affect seaport development. Kim (1993) noted that shippers in Korea are concerned with distance between origin and destination, loading hours, cargo handling, trucking, and cost. Notteboom *et al.* (2000) realized from their findings that there is a correlation between port size and seaport efficiency. According to Burns (2015), the main objective of ports' strategic location may be based on generating income or a competitive advantage. In practice, maritime industry is volatile, characterized by unexpected fluctuations between the forces of demand and supply. Ports are influenced by politics, trade agreements, currency, volatile trade prices, security, and wars.

The strategic location of a port can be based on global capital markets, the demand and supply of factors of production, transit areas like the Suez or Panama Canals, Free Port or Free Trade Zones, value added trade centers, shipbuilding, etc. The logistics and location of a seaport must be properly guided by the transshipment location, dimension of the port, hinterland economic dimension, port efficiency dimension, and cost dimension (Onifade, 2020).

The significance of these theories to the study is that, first, port like every other product has a life cycle which go through the phases of introduction, growth, maturity, decline and eventually death if nothing is done at the maturity stage to revive it. Nigeria's ports have gone through these phases and perhaps due to poor plan of obsolescence have been allowed to rot thereby creating a problem of infrastructure deficit and subsequently, inefficiency in service delivery. Thus, for the maritime industry to live to its full potentials of enhancing seaborne trade, there must be adequate planning to reduce most of the constraining factors that could result in port failures and eventual collapse. Again, the theory of location point to the fact that

effective operation of ports' activities required link between one port and another through workable infrastructure such as roads, rail, communication and ship repairs and maintenance yards. The frequency of ship berth cannot be removed from availability of such infrastructure that make such activities possible.

Empirics

In this section, empirical studies on the relationship between maritime infrastructure and maritime industry are reviewed. The essence is to identify the likely missing links between the two.

Omoke *et al.* (2015) examined the effect of privatization on the performance of Nigerian seaports, using pre- and post-privatization data. A Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon (MWW) test was applied to data (secondary) on two major indices of port operation (average berth occupancy and average turn-around time). The result of the analysis showed that on average, the berth occupancy and turn-around time improved from 51.35% to 72.47% and 8.18 days to 4.83 days respectively. It was also found that at a 0.05 level of significance, the concession of Nigerian ports has significantly improved average berth occupancy and average turnaround time of the vessels calling at Nigerian ports.

Bello (2017) examined the ways and manners concessionaires (terminal operators) of Nigerian seaports have over the years manage and develop port infrastructures in order to gain insights into shipping operational development in the country. Specifically, the study assessed the level of infrastructural developments with a view to showcasing the areas that need more attention both by the terminal operators and the government and examined the relationship between investment by the operators and cargo throughput at the ports after it has been concessioned. The results from the findings indicated that, though ports have improved in terms of infrastructural developments especially in the area of cargo handling equipment infrastructures, warehousing, Quay development, yet, there is need for improvement of rail transport infrastructure and development in shipbuilding.

Bassey and Nsa (2018) assessed the problems and prospects of developing inland water transportation in Nigeria with Calabar River as a case study. The study adopted the survey research design, stratified sampling technique was used in selecting the sampled population of the study. Findings revealed that there was no significant relationship between the provision of inland transportation facilities/services and level of socio-economic development in the study area. The study also revealed that the development of the water transportation system in the area could have positive impact on trade and commerce, job creation, revenue generation, provide tourism among others.

Benson and David (2018) empirically investigated the impact of an effective shipping policy instrument on the development of the Maritime sector in Nigeria. Data were collated in Lagos, Nigeria through a structured questionnaires administered to stakeholders of the maritime sector in Nigeria. The method of analysis used in the study was a simple non-parametric (chi-square test) statistical method. From the method of analysis, the study found out that an effective shipping policy affect the development of the maritime sector in Nigeria.

Nwokedi *et al.* (2019) investigated the principal component constraints to ship building development in Nigeria. Adopting the theory of constraint approach, survey research design was used in which primary data were obtained from questionnaire responses from employees and management staff of shipyards in the ship building clusters in Lagos, Port-Harcourt and Warri. It was found that the principal component constraints to the development of the ship building sector in Nigeria include financial constraint, infrastructural constraint and poor skill and technical know-how.

Okoroafor (2020) examined the relationship between cargo handling equipment and efficient cargo delivery in Nigerian Ports. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey in its investigation of the variables. The result of the findings further revealed that tractor-trailer system, and heavy duty forklift system gave rise to efficient cargo delivery in Nigerian Ports. The study recommended that management of ports in Nigeria should devise strategies for successful operation of handling equipment which should involve devising ways to compensate for a number of factors that, individually or in combination, act to reduce the efficiency of their equipment.

Onifade (2020) examined the prospects and challenges of the development of proposed Apapa and Calabar seaports and to analyze the efficiencies of the two selected seaports in order to determine the need for the required investment in seaport development. Descriptive analysis was used to examine the challenges of the selected seaports, while stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) was used to determine the efficiency of the selected seaports. It was discovered that the challenges associated with the Calabar Seaport were the draught level, cost of shipment, accessibility to industries, and condition of other modes of transport. By implication, the congestion in the seaports in the Lagos seaport complex with the maximum level of efficiency creates the need for another seaport, which must be sited at a well-vetted location. Hence, investment decisions regarding whether to build a new seaport or use dredging to upgrade the existing ones must be carefully analyzed, as the establishment of the proposed Ibom deep seaport may further affect the efficiency of the Calabar seaport(s). In conclusion, demand should be the driving force for port establishment: when a port cannot generate enough traffic, it may not yield returns on investment as expected.

The success of maritime trade relies majorly on the volume and quality of infrastructure available. Port has been repeatedly established to be one of the major infrastructure in maritime business because other infrastructure has their link to the port. From the theory of dry port, it is obvious that port like any other product emerges and go through the cycle to extinction. In this stead, there should be plan to redesign it in case of obsolescence. The number of ship that can berth at a given port is a function of the level and quality of infrastructure in that port. The higher the ability of a port to handle cargo, the higher the amount of revenue it will generate. There is therefore the need for every stakeholder in the maritime industry to ensure smooth working infrastructure through proper policy formulation and implementation. Building workable infrastructure for the maritime industry is sure to promote international trade and economic growth and development.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study sought to investigate the relationship between shipping business and maritime infrastructure in Nigeria. In view of the objective of the study, the study adopted a correlational research approach. Correlational studies can be prediction studies or relationship studies. Relationship studies usually study the relationship between measures of different variables obtained at almost the same time. While prediction studies are concerned with measuring a variable that can be used to predict some future events. Justification for the use of this approach is predicated on the fact that the performance of shipping business in Nigeria can be measured simultaneously by a number of inter-related variables that constitute maritime infrastructure.

3.2 Model Specification

Correlational approach adopted for the study indicates that a relationship exists between the endogenous variable and the exogenous variables. Consequently, following the theory of constraint, the relationship between maritime infrastructure and shipping business in Nigeria can be constrained by some factors such as dearth of infrastructure in the industry. Again, following the objectives of the study, it can be established that, there exist a relationship whether positive or negative between maritime infrastructure and shipping business in Nigeria. If shipping business is proxied by ship traffic(throughput), average turnaround time and average waiting time at berth and maritime infrastructure by number of ship, vessel capacity (gross registered tonnage) and quality of port infrastructure, then, the objectives of the study can be modelled as:

$$CTr = f(Nsh, GRT, QPI) \text{-----} (1).$$

$$STT = f(Nsh, GRT, QPI) \text{-----}(2)$$

$$AWT = f(Nsh, GRT, QPI) \text{-----}(3)$$

Equation (1) implies that, ship traffic is a function of number of ship, vessel capacity and the port infrastructure. Equation (2) implies that, turnaround time is a function of number of ship, vessel capacity and the port infrastructure. Consequently, Equation (3) implies that average waiting time at berth is a function of number of ship, vessel capacity and the port infrastructure. Items on the left hand side of the equations are proxy for shipping business while items on the right hand side are proxy for maritime infrastructure.

Expressing (1), (2) and (3) econometrically, the three equations appear thus;

$$\text{Str} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{Nsh} + \beta_2 \text{GRT} + \beta_3 \text{QPI} + e_i \text{-----(4)}$$

Where, Str = ship traffic; Nsh = number of ship; GRT = vessel capacity and QPI = port infrastructure, e_i = error term.

$$\text{STT} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{Nsh} + \beta_2 \text{GRT} + \beta_3 \text{QPI} + e_i \text{-----(5)}$$

Where, GrT = gross tonnage and

$$\text{AWT} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{Nsh} + \beta_2 \text{Vcap} + \beta_3 \text{Pcap} + e_i \text{-----(6)}$$

Where, AWT = average waiting time at berth

Other variables are as earlier defined.

$$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 \geq 0$$

3.3 Description of Variables

Ship traffic or cargo throughput measures the amount of cargo or number of vessels the port authority handles overtime.

Gross Registered Tonnage refers to record of internal volume (internal capacity) of ships or water going vessels used as a means for categorizing commercial vessels.

The average turnaround time corresponds to the average difference between date of departure and date of arrival among all container vessels calling at a port (or country) within one month of navigation. The unit is the number of days per call.

The time awaiting at berth is the time vessels waited at sea for green light to be taken by pilot to ports. Once vessel arrived at docks to unload the cargo, it can be call vessel (ship) berthed. If more congestion is there in a port, arrived vessel may have to wait for long period to get berthed.

Quality of port infrastructure index represents an assessment of the quality of port facilities in a given country and measures port infrastructural development in Nigerian ports.

3.4 Data Source

Data for all variables in the study were obtained from CBN statistical bulletin,

National Bureau of Statistics bulletin, Nigeria Port Authority Bulletin and World Development indicators several years.

Estimation Technique and procedure

Data collected were first subjected to test of stationarity using Augmented Dickey Fuller test statistics to ascertain the level of integration of each variable. Thereafter, ordinary least square estimation technique in logarithm form was used to estimate the relationship among the variables of interest.

4 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

In this section, the results of the findings are presented and analysed in line with the objectives of the study.

4.1 Test of stationarity - Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF	1%	5%	10%	1(d)
AWT	-4.469708	-3.920350	-3.065585	-2.673459	1(0)***
CRT	-6.377071	-4.532598	-3.673616	-3.277364	1(1)***
GTR	-4.100125	-3.831511	-3.029970	-2.655194	1(1)***
NSH	-5.700317	-3.831511	-3.029970	-2.655194	1(1)***
QPI	-4.714073		-3.029970	-2.655194	
		-3.831511			1(1)***
STT	-4.903249	-3.831511	-3.029970	-2.655194	1(1)***
TEU	-5.573226	-3.857386	-3.040391	-2.660551	1(1)***

*** significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

From the test of stationarity presented above, all the variables are stationary at first difference except average waiting time which is stationary at level. It therefore means that there is cointegration among the variables in addition to the fact they can be used at their level of integration without the possibility of spurious regression.

4.2 Analysis of Research Objectives

Research Objective One

Table 4.2 Relationship Between Ship Traffic and Maritime Infrastructure

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	16.14072	1.274629	12.66307	0.0000
GRT	5.46E-09	3.95E-09	1.383248	0.1845
NSH	0.000282	0.000292	0.964881	0.3481
QPI	-0.054772	0.177035	-0.309387	0.7608
R-squared	0.294716	Mean dependent var	17.78940	
Adjusted R-squared	0.170254	S.D. dependent var	0.584641	
S.E. of regression	0.532552	Akaike info criterion	1.747371	
Sum squared resid	4.821399	Schwarz criterion	1.946328	
Log likelihood	-14.34740	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.790550	
F-statistic	2.367917	Durbin-Watson stat	2.135302	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.106799			

Ship traffic is represented by cargo throughput. If maritime infrastructure is represented by gross registered tonnage, number of ship and quality of port infrastructure, it can be seen from the result that none of the proxy for maritime relate significantly with ship traffic. It goes to show that the available infrastructure does not encourage shipping business in Nigeria. Furthermore, quality of port infrastructure is negatively insignificantly related to cargo throughput.

Research Objective Two

Table 4.3 Relationship Between Ship Turnaround Time and Maritime Infrastructure

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	5.357480	3.910458	1.370039	0.1939
GRT	-4.17E-08	4.30E-08	-0.970288	0.3496
GRT(-1)	1.99E-08	2.20E-08	0.904532	0.3822
NSH	0.000206	0.000816	0.252594	0.8045
NSH(-1)	0.000463	0.000882	0.525085	0.6084
QPI	-0.828101	0.467312	-1.772053	0.0998
QPI(-1)	0.485497	1.152714	0.421177	0.6805

R-squared	0.673289	Mean dependent var	5.629500
Adjusted R-squared	0.522500	S.D. dependent var	1.863196
S.E. of regression	1.287495	Akaike info criterion	3.612491
Sum squared resid	21.54935	Schwarz criterion	3.960997
Log likelihood	-29.12491	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.680523
F-statistic	4.465091	Durbin-Watson stat	1.608936
Prob(F-statistic)	0.011418		

Elements of maritime infrastructure do not relate significantly with Ship turnaround time. Quality of port infrastructure has negative and non-significant relations with ship turnaround time. However, the one term lag of this variable has positive non-significant relations with ship turnaround time.

Research Objective Three

Table 4.4 Relationship Between Average Time Awaiting Berth and Maritime Infrastructure

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.649210	1.967305	0.330000	0.7467
GRT	-8.05E-09	2.16E-08	-0.372107	0.7158
GRT(-1)	1.10E-08	1.11E-08	0.992809	0.3389
NSH	-0.000195	0.000410	-0.474055	0.6433
NSH(-1)	0.000570	0.000443	1.284342	0.2214
QPI	-0.379908	0.235099	-1.615947	0.1301
QPI(-1)	-0.095260	0.579917	-0.164264	0.8720
R-squared	0.493239	Mean dependent var	1.543500	
Adjusted R-squared	0.259350	S.D. dependent var	0.752632	
S.E. of regression	0.647723	Akaike info criterion	2.238511	
Sum squared resid	5.454091	Schwarz criterion	2.587017	
Log likelihood	-15.38511	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.306543	
F-statistic	2.108855	Durbin-Watson stat	2.547700	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.122206			

From the result above, the relationship between all elements of maritime infrastructure and average time awaiting berth are negative and non-significant except for the one time lag of number of ship and gross registered tonnage which are positively yet non-significantly related with average time awaiting berth. Yet, quality of port infrastructure both in its current and lag state is negatively and insignificantly related with average ship turnaround time.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between ship traffic and maritime infrastructure in Nigeria.

From the result of the analysis presented in the table 4.2 above, it can be said that there is no significant relationship between ship traffic and maritime infrastructure in Nigeria. On the basis of this, the null hypothesis of non-significant relationship is accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between ship turnaround time and maritime infrastructure in Nigeria.

Taking the result of the analysis in the table 4.3 above, none of the elements of maritime infrastructure shows significant relationship with ship turnaround time. In view of this, it can be said that there is no significant relationship between ship turnaround time and maritime infrastructure. Again, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between average time awaiting berth and maritime infrastructure in Nigeria.

Looking at the result of the analysis in the table 4.4 above, it can be said that there is no significant relationship between average time awaiting berth and maritime infrastructure in Nigeria. Thus, the null hypothesis of non-significant relationship is accepted.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Infrastructure be it physical or soft is critical to the growth of an economy. This study attempted to examine the relationship between shipping business and maritime infrastructure in Nigeria. Efficient and workable maritime infrastructure is deemed necessary for the increase in the amount of cargo or number of vessels the port authority handles overtime (throughput). It is also necessary for the reduction in ship

turnaround time and also a reduction in average time awaiting berth. Poor maritime infrastructure can aggravate any of the situations mentioned here. From the analysis, it is obvious that maritime infrastructure in Nigeria does not impact significantly on any of the shipping activities used in the study. It goes to show why Nigeria is not making much revenue from shipping business and the reason why there is reduction in the number of shipping lines in Nigeria. No investor would want to invest in an infrastructural deficit environment because the expected return on investment may not be realized. The poor state of maritime infrastructure no doubt reflects the poor state of governance in Nigeria which manifest in manifold corruption in almost all sectors of the economy. There is therefore need for policy somersault in the maritime sector if Nigeria is to derive maximum benefits from her rich maritime resource endowment.

Maritime industry is very critical to the growth of any economy. The extent to which this sector can contribute to the growth of any economy is the function of how it is maintained. When a country maritime sector is properly equipped to play its roles among other sectors of the economy, the country GDP will increase, the revenue base of the country will increase and the rate of youth unemployment will reduce. However, paucity of infrastructure in this sector of the economy has portends more woes for the economy. The rate of ship traffic to Nigeria's ports has reduced, ship turnaround time at the ports have increased over time and average time required for ship waiting at the sea to berth has also increased. All these are due to poor port infrastructure in most of the ports in Nigeria. The non-significant relationship between maritime infrastructure and shipping business in Nigeria no doubt portends poor state of governance in Nigeria and therefore requires radical policy approach to reverse the trend.

Maritime infrastructure development like every other infrastructure in the economy should be given utmost priority if the country is to reap bountifully from her huge maritime resource endowment. Promotion of good governance by controlling corruption and ensuring government effectiveness should be given more attention not just paying lip service.

Port infrastructure and other maritime infrastructure could be improved through diligent concessionary arrangement. Apart from maintaining the existing port, there is need to decongest the over bloated port by building and expanding new ports in the country such as Ibom deep sea port.

References

- Afolabi, T.O. (2015). Building Economic Capacity Through Maritime Infrastructure Development. Being a paper presented at A 3-Day Annual Exhibition & Conference – Nigeria: Regenerating Economic Growth through the Maritime Sector organized by Nigeria Maritime Expo (Nimarex) 2015 at Eko Hotel & Suites, Victoria Island, Lagos. Tuesday, 7 July, 2015.
- Akinlola, B. (2015). A case for shipbuilding and repair yards. From <https://www.shipsandports.com>
- American Association of Ports Authority (AAPA) (2014). Maritime Information Infrastructure – A Key Component of the U.S. 21st Century Freight Movement Network.
- Alstadt, B. (2012). The relationship of transportation access and connectivity to economic outcomes. *Transportation Research Record*, 2297, 154-162.
- Bassey, S.I., and Nsa, M. E. (2018). Problems and Prospects of Developing Inland Water Transportation in Nigeria: The Case of Calabar River. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 23(7), 27-37.
- Bello, K. (2017). Assessment of Seaports Post-concession Infrastructure Maintenance and Development in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Management*, 6(3), 11-17.
- Benson, I.A., and David, O.O. (2018). An empirical investigation of the impact of effective shipping policy instrument on the development of the Nigeria maritime industry. *African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 1(1), 79-83.
- Burns, M.C. (2015). *Port Operations and Management*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press
- Brickstone (2019). Private Sector Participation in the Maritime Industry.
- Clark, X., Dollar, D., Micco, A., (2004). Port efficiency, maritime transport costs, and bilateral trade. *Journal of Development Economics*, 75, 417-450.
- Ducruet, C., Cuyala, S., Hosni, A.E., (2016). The changing influence of city-systems on global shipping networks: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Shipping Trade* 1(4).

- Ekeada, P., Obioma, U., and Anyanwu, J.O., (2018). Examining the Productivity of the Nigerian Shipping Industry. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: E Marketing*, 18(2), 10-17.
- Ekpo, E.I. (2012). Impact of Shipping on Nigerian Economy: Implications for Sustainable Development. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 2(7), 107-117.
- Ellis, P. D. (2011) Social ties and international entrepreneurship: opportunities and constraints affecting firm internationalization. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 42(1), 99-127.
- Fashakin, R. (2017). High customs duties killed ship yards, ship building in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.shippingposition.com>
- Goldratt, Eliyahu, M. (1984). *Essays on the Theory of Constraints*. Great Barrington, MA: North River Press.
- Goldratt, E. M. (2004). *The Goal: A Process of Ongoing Improvement*. NY: North River Press.
- Gordon, J. R., Lee, P. M., Lucas, H.C., (2005). A resource-based view of competitive advantage at the port of Singapore. *Journal of Strategic Information System*, 14(1), 69–86.
- Grossmann, I., (2008). Perspectives for Hamburg as a port city in the context of a changing global environment. *Geoforum*, 39(6), 2062–2072.
- Haezendonck, E. and Notteboom, T. (2002). The Competitive Advantage of Seaports. In Huybrechts, M. (Ed.), *Port Competitiveness: An Economic and Legal Analysis of the Factors Determining the Competitiveness of Seaports* (pp. 67–87), Antwerp, Belgium: De Boeck.
- Hausman, W. H., Lee, H. L., Subramanian, U. (2013). The impact of logistics performance on trade. *Production Operation Manager*, 22(2), 236–252.
- Heaver, T., Meersman, H., Van de Voorde, E. Co-operation and competition in international container transport: Strategies for ports. *Maritius Policy Management*, 28, 293–305.

- Hesse, M., (2006). Global chain, local pain: regional implications of global distribution networks in the German north range. *Growth Change* 37(4), 570–596
- Ibeawuchi C. N. and Okeudo, G. N. (2013). Empirical Evaluation of the Maritime Industry's impact on the Nigerian Economy. *International Journal of Current Research*, 5(6), 1355-1359,
- Ikpoku, N.M., (2021). Barriers to Technology Adoption Among Maritime Industry Stakeholders in Nigeria. *Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies*.
- Infrastructure Report Card (2021). Available at www.infrastructurereportcard.org
- Kim, H. S. (1993). *Decision Components of Shippers' Port Choice in Korea*. Korea Maritime Institute: Seoul, Korea.
- Korinek, J. and Sourdin P. (2011). To what extent are high-quality logistics services trade facilitating? OECD Trade Policy Papers, No. 108. OECD publishing, Paris.
- Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (2004) *Principles of Marketing*, 10th edition. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education.
- Lakshmanan, T. (2011) The broader economic consequences of transport infrastructure investments. *Journal of Transport Geogr*, 19(1), 1–12
- Levinson, M., (2006). *The Box: How the Shipping Container Made the World Smaller and the World Economy Bigger*, Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- Limao, N., and Venables, A. J., (2001) Infrastructure, geographical disadvantage, transport costs, and trade. *World Bank Economic Review*, 15(3), 451–479
- Lloyd, C., Onyeabor, E., Nwafor, N., Alozie, O.J., Nwafor, M. G., Mahakweabba, U., & Adibe, E. (2020). Maritime transportation and the Nigerian economy: matters arising, *Commonwealth Law Bulletin*.
- Munim, Z. H. and Schramm, H. J. (2017). Forecasting container shipping freight rates for the Far East – Northern Europe trade lane. *Maritius Economic Logistic*, 19(1), 106–125.

- Munim, Z. H. and Schramm, H-H., (2018). The impacts of port infrastructure and logistics performance on economic growth: the mediating role of seaborne trade. *Journal of Shipping and Trade*, 3, 1.
- National Bureau of Statistics/Nigerian Ports Authority, (2017). Shipping and Port Related Activities Data. Available at: <http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/report/507>
- Nguyen, P.Q.P., (2018). The development of marine infrastructure is the key to promote the maritime economy. *Worldwide Journal of Multidisciplinary research and Development*; 167-171.
- Notteboom, T., Coeck, C. and Van Den Broeck, J. (200). Measuring and explaining the relative efficiency of container terminals by means of Bayesian stochastic frontier models. *International Journal of Maritius Economics*, 2, 83–106.
- Nwokedi, T.C., Kalu, D.I., Igboanusi, C.C. Addah, G.L., and Odumodu, C.U., (2019). Constraint Theory Approach Analysis of the Nigerian Shipbuilding Industry. *Scientific Journal on Transport and Logistics*, 1(1), 50-61.
- Nwokedi, T. C., Ndikom, O. C., Hussaini, Y. K., Komolafe, B. O. and Okonko, I. I. (2020). Economic justification for development and operationalization of rail-freight-corridors between hub-seaports and inland container depots in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development of Transport and Logistics*, 5(2), 73-89.
- Okoroafor, P. U., (2020). Cargo Handling Equipment and Efficient Cargo Delivery in Nigerian Ports. *International Journal of Business & Entrepreneurship Research*, 13(2), 26 - 42
- Olapoju, O.M. (2019). Assessing the contribution of containerization to the Development of Western Ports, Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of International Logistics and Trade*; 17(1), 12-20
- Olufemi, A. K., Okeudo, G. N., Ejem. E.A. and Declan, N. D. (2021). Development of Port Infrastructure and Service Quality in Nigerian Ports. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 9(6), 25-32.
- Omoke, V., Diugwu, I. A., Nwaogbe, O. R., Ibe, C. C. and Ekpe, D. A. (2015). Infrastructure Financing and Management: The Impact of Concession on the Operations and Performance of Nigerian Seaports. *Journal of*

Behavioural Economics, Finance, Entrepreneurship, Accounting and Transport, 3(2), 65-70.

Omoke V., Aturu A. C., Nwaogbe O.R., Ajiboye, A.O. and Diugwu I. (2018). Analysis of the Impact of Port Operations on Nigerian Economy: A Focus on Apapa Seaport. *Research gate*.

Onifade, A.O. (2020). New Seaport Development-Prospects and Challenges: Perspectives from Apapa and Calabar Seaports, Nigeria. www.mdpi.com/journal/logistics

Onwuegbuchunam, D.E., Okeke, K.O., Aponjolosun, M.O., Igboanusi, C. and Nwosu, A.C. (2021) Utilization of Cargo Handling Facilities in Nigerian Seaports. *Open Journal of Safety Science and Technology*, 11, 143-157.

Osadume, R.C., and Edih O., (2020). Port Revenue Performance and Economic Growth: The Nigerian Ports Authority Experience, 2010-2019. *LOGI – Scientific Journal on Transport and Logistics*, 11(2), 1-11.

Owoputi A. E., (2014). Issues in Safety and Security in Maritime Transportation, Port and Marine Environment. *Journal of Engineering and Engineering Technology*, 8(2), 74-81.

Panayides P.M., Parola, F., and Lam, J. S. L. (2015). The effect of institutional factors on public–private partnership success in ports. *Transp Res A Policy Pract* 71, 110–127

Parola, F., Risitano, M., Ferretti, M. and Panetti, E. (2017). The drivers of port competitiveness: A critical review. *Transportation Review*, 37, 116–138.

Portugal-Perez, A., Wilson, J.S., (2012). Export performance and trade facilitation reform: hard and soft infrastructure. *World Development*, 40(7), 1295–1307

Qui, M., Fredendall, L., & Zhu, Z. (2002). TOC or LP? [production control]. *Manufacturing Engineer*, 81(4), 190–195.

Shan J, Yu M. and Lee C. Y. (2014). An empirical investigation of the seaport's economic impact: evidence from major ports in China. *Transport Res E-Log*, 69, 41–53.

Slack, B. and Gouvernal, E. (2015) Container transshipment and logistics in the context of urban economic development. *Growth Change*, 47(3), 406–415.

- Subramanian, U., Anderson, W. P. and Lee, K. (2005). Measuring the impact of the investment climate on total factor productivity: the cases of China and Brazil. Working paper No. 3792, The World Bank, Washington, DC.
- UNCTAD. (2009). Review of Maritime Transport. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, Geneva.
- Urry, J., (2007). *Mobilities*. Cambridge: Polity.
- Venables, A. J., Laird J. & Overman H. (2014). Transport investment and economic performance: Implications for project appraisal. <https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/>
- Watts, R.B., (2005). Maritime Critical Infrastructure Protection: Multi-Agency Command and Control in an Asymmetric Environment. *Homeland Security Affairs*, 1(2), 3, 1-12.
- Wilmsmeier G, Hoffmann J (2008) Liner shipping connectivity and port infrastructure as determinants of freight rates in the Caribbean. *Maritius Economic Logistic*, 10(1–2), 130–151.
- Yeo, G.T., Roe, M. and Dinwoodie, J. (2008). Evaluating the competitiveness of container ports in Korea and China. *Transp Res A Policy Pract.* 42(6), 910–921.